

Supplementary Materials for:

Models and data of AMPLify: a deep learning tool for antimicrobial peptide prediction

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Performance analysis on the balanced and imbalanced models of AMPlify

Table S1 compares the performance of the AMPlify balanced and imbalanced models, which were trained on the balanced and imbalanced training sets respectively and assessed on the balanced test set. Three other AMP prediction tools (iAMP-2L [1], iAMPpred [2], and AMP Scanner Vr.2 [3]) that were used for comparison in our previous work [4] are listed in addition to the AMPlify models. The performance of the AMPlify balanced model and the three comparators was taken from our previous work [4]. The imbalanced model of AMPlify only outperforms the balanced model in sensitivity (94.37% vs. 92.93%). The balanced model of AMPlify outperforms the imbalanced model in accuracy (93.71% vs. 89.22%), specificity (94.49% vs. 84.07%), F1 score (93.66% vs. 89.75%), and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) (98.37% vs. 96.88%). Even though our imbalanced model does not perform as well as the balanced model on the balanced test set in general, it still surpasses our three comparators by at least 10.72% in accuracy, 3.71% in sensitivity, 16.41% in specificity, 8.92% in F1 score, and 8.55% in AUROC.

Table S1: Performance comparison among different tools on the balanced test set. Values of accuracy (acc), sensitivity (sens), specificity (spec), F1 score (F1) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) are presented in percentage.

Tool	Model	Acc	Sens	Spec	F1	AUROC
iAMPpred	original ^a	74.01	87.90	60.12	77.18	80.70
iAMP-2L	original ^a	77.96	88.26	67.66	80.02	-
AMP Scanner Vr.2	original ^a	78.50	90.66	66.35	80.83	88.33
AMPlify	balanced	93.71	92.93	94.49	93.66	98.37
	imbalanced	89.22	94.37	84.07	89.75	96.88

^aModels presented in the referenced papers and are available through online servers.

Table S2 shows the same comparison but assessing the performance of all the models on the imbalanced test set. We note that the online server of iAMP-2L [1] was down at the time this analysis was done (Nov 11, 2022), so its results were not compared here. In this comparison, the AMPlify imbalanced model outperforms the balanced model in all five metrics of accuracy (98.94% vs. 95.97%), sensitivity (94.37% vs. 92.93%), specificity (99.09% vs. 96.06%), F1 score (84.87% vs. 59.19%), and AUROC (99.54% vs. 98.06%). However, our balanced model still beats the best comparator, AMP Scanner Vr.2, by 24.71% in accuracy, 2.27% in sensitivity, 25.43% in specificity, 42.62% in F1 score, and 6.62% in AUROC.

Table S2: Performance comparison among different tools on the imbalanced test set. Values of accuracy (acc), sensitivity (sens), specificity (spec), F1 score (F1) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) are presented in percentage.

Tool	Model	Acc	Sens	Spec	F1	AUROC
iAMPpred	original ^a	14.29	87.90	11.90	6.07	55.54
AMP Scanner Vr.2	original ^a	71.26	90.66	70.63	16.57	91.44
AMPlify	balanced	95.97	92.93	96.06	59.19	98.06
	imbalanced	98.94	94.37	99.09	84.87	99.54

^aModels presented in the referenced papers and are available through online servers.

Generally speaking, the AMPlify balanced model performs better on the balanced test set while the AMPlify imbalanced model performs better on the imbalanced test set. The difference in balanced and imbalanced model performance mainly lies in the change in the distribution of the training data. The imbalanced set reflects a more natural scenario where antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are only a small portion of all occurring peptide sequences, while the balanced set looks more into sequences that are similar in lengths to the known AMP sequences [4] (AMPs are mostly short sequences [5]). These two models have their own usages depending on the features of the candidate peptide sequence sets for filtering. In cases where the input consists of a large sequence set with the number of non-AMPs far greater than that of AMPs (e.g. transcriptomics data sets), the imbalanced model would be a better choice since it may be desirable to reduce the number of false positives to a minimum in order to cut downstream synthesis and analysis costs (the imbalanced model obtains a high specificity of 99.09% on the imbalanced test set). On the other hand, the balanced model is better at filtering through relatively curated data sets (e.g. annotated through sequence homology search, length or charge filtering), similarly to how we applied AMPlify in our previous work [4].

References

1. Xiao X, Wang P, Lin W-Z, Jia J-H, Chou K-C. iAMP-2L: A two-level multi-label classifier for identifying antimicrobial peptides and their functional types. *Anal Biochem.* 2013;436:168–77.
2. Meher PK, Sahu TK, Saini V, Rao AR. Predicting antimicrobial peptides with improved accuracy by incorporating the compositional, physico-chemical and structural features into Chou’s general PseAAC. *Sci Rep.* 2017;7:42362.
3. Veltri D, Kamath U, Shehu A. Deep learning improves antimicrobial peptide recognition. *Bioinformatics.* 2018;34:2740–7.

4. Li C, Sutherland D, Hammond SA, Yang C, Taho F, Bergman L, et al. AMPLify: attentive deep learning model for discovery of novel antimicrobial peptides effective against WHO priority pathogens. *BMC Genomics*. 2022;23:77.
5. Zhang L, Gallo RL. Antimicrobial peptides. *Curr Biol*. 2016;26:R14–9.